

Using EPG for balanced sequences

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In *balanced* MR-STAT¹ or MRF (MR Fingerprinting²) technology, the signal model used in the reconstruction process usually does not involve Extended Phase Graphs³ (EPG). In this memo, it is briefly explained that this may be useful nevertheless, particularly if we want the acquisition+reconstruction system to separately estimate T_2 and T_2' , which are two mutually independent properties of tissue.

In the non-balanced coherently-spoiled approach, modelling of the signal at any point in time is done using the EPG model, taking F_0 (the 0th order transverse EPG component) as representing the signal at the echo. For balanced sequences, the EPG model is typically not used – the Bloch model is used instead.

Here, it is suggested to use the EPG model for balanced sequences as well; but instead of taking F_0 for the signal, a weighted sum of almost-overlapping EPG-states is used. This is expressed as

$$\rho \sum_k w_k F_k,$$

where F_k represents the occupancy of the k -th order transverse EPG state (which is a function of the RF sequence up to that timepoint, of relaxation parameters T_1 and T_2 and of B_1^+); ρ represents spin-density and w_k is a correction factor, elaborated below.

In the ideal case where all spins are on-resonance and there is no inhomogeneity (whether microscopic or macroscopic), all EPG states fully contribute to the signal, i.e. $w_k = 1$ for all k .

In the situation with no microscopic inhomogeneities ($T_2^* = T_2$, i.e., $R_2' = 0$), but in the presence of a main field deviation B_0 , we have to add the transverse states by taking into account their mutual dephasing, i.e. $w_k = e^{i\gamma B_0 T_R k}$ (if the signal were to be acquired right after each excitation pulse), or, more realistically, $w_k = e^{i\gamma B_0 (T_R k + T_E)}$.

The situation is different when $R_2' = T_2^{*-1} - T_2^{-1}$ is nonzero. In that situation, we have to take into account a distribution of microscopical (but static!) field deviations within any voxel. Such distribution is modelled as a Lorentzian distribution, which is compatible with an exponentially decaying signal-model^{4,5}. So we model the probability density p of the magnetic field deviation B as

$$p(B) = \frac{R_2' / (\gamma\pi)}{(R_2' / \gamma)^2 + B^2}$$

This leads to the following expression of the signal:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{R_2' / (\gamma\pi)}{(R_2' / \gamma)^2 + B^2} \left(\rho \sum_k F_k e^{i\gamma B_0 (T_R k + T_E)} e^{i\gamma B (T_R k + T_E)} \right) dB$$

This can be rewritten as

$$\rho \sum_k F_k e^{i\gamma B_0(T_R k + T_E)} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{R_2' / (\gamma \pi)}{(R_2' / \gamma)^2 + B^2} e^{i\gamma B(T_R k + T_E)} dB.$$

The integral evaluates to $e^{-R_2'|T_R k|}$. Herewith, the expression becomes

$$\rho \sum_k F_k e^{i\gamma B_0(T_R k + T_E)} e^{-R_2'|T_R k + T_E|}.$$

If needed, this can be extended to a multispectral water+fat case,

$$\sum_k \left[e^{i\gamma B_0(T_R k + T_E)} e^{-R_2'|T_R k + T_E|} \left(\rho_W + \rho_F \sum_c p_c e^{i2\pi f_c(T_R k + T_E)} \right) \right] F_k$$

(with f_c the frequencies and p_c the relative strength of the fat spectral model – these are known constants.)

Since the set of transverse EPG-state occupancies F_k are function of T_1 , T_2 and of B_1^+ , the whole expression is a function of T_1 , T_2 , T_2' (or R_2'), B_1^+ , B_0 , ρ_W and ρ_F . Given enough data, these can be reconstructed via an appropriately extended MR-STAT reconstruction process.

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